

Development and characterization of Ibuprofen-loaded self-emulsifying drug delivery systems

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Abstract

Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems are a lipid-based technological approach with immense promise in enhancing the oral bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs. The aim of the present study is to develop and characterize self-emulsifying drug delivery systems of Ibuprofen using medium-chain (MCT) and long-chain triglyceride (LCT) oils, Tween 80 and RH-40 as surfactants, and ethanol, polyethylene glycol 400, and propylene glycol as co-surfactants. Twelve formulations have been prepared, with the components and their ratios derived through solubility studies and construction of pseudoternary phase diagrams. All formulations have been characterized through Fourier transform IR spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermodynamic stability studies, accelerated stability studies, percent transmittance, droplet size and zeta-potential analysis, and *in vitro* drug release studies. The results indicate that self-emulsifying drug delivery systems are a promising approach for enhancing the solubility, and the rate and extent of release of Ibuprofen. The advantages of the combination of medium-chain triglycerides and Cremophor RH-40 are evident.

Keywords

Ibuprofen, SEDDS, medium-chain triglycerides, droplet size, *in vitro* release study

Introduction

Ibuprofen (2-(4-(2-methylpropyl) phenyl) propanoic acid) is a widely used non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), a non-selective inhibitor of the cyclooxygenase enzymes COX-1 and COX-2 used for relief of symptoms of arthritis and fever. Ibuprofen has lipophilic properties and is poorly soluble in water. It belongs to class II of the Biopharmaceutical classification system with low solubility and high permeability through the cell membranes. The rate-limiting step in the absorption of Ibuprofen from the gastrointestinal tract is the dissolution rate, which necessitates the study of

different methods to increase solubility and hence bioavailability (Higgins et al. 2001; Potthast et al. 2005; Bushra and Aslam 2010; Mazaleuskaya et al. 2015). Many methods have been investigated to enhance the solubility of Ibuprofen, including micronization, crystal engineering, solid dispersions, cyclodextrins, solid lipid nanoparticles, microemulsions, and self-emulsifying and self-microemulsifying drug delivery systems (Mihaylov et al. 2025).

In recent years, research aimed at improving the solubility and bioavailability of Ibuprofen through the use of self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS) has been of interest. SEDDS are a lipid-based technological approach

with immense promise in enhancing the oral bioavailability of hydrophobic drugs. Self-emulsifying formulations are an isotropic mixture of drug, lipid (natural or synthetic oils), and emulsifiers (liquid or solid), usually with one or more hydrophilic co-solvents/co-emulsifiers (Singh et al. 2009; Kohli et al. 2010). Upon mild agitation followed by dilution in aqueous media, such as GI fluids, these systems can form fine oil-in-water (o/w) emulsions or microemulsions. Self-emulsifying formulations produce emulsions with a droplet size between 100 and 300 nm, while self-microemulsifying formulations form transparent microemulsions with a droplet size of less than 50 nm. As compared to conventional emulsions, which require high shear to form a dispersion, SEDDS preparation involves a simple process of dissolving the drug in oil followed by mixing it with surfactants and co-surfactants. Conventional emulsions display multiple instabilities such as creaming, coalescence, breaking, and phase inversion. On the other hand, SEDDS formulations are physically stable, as they are clear, isotropic mixtures immune to small changes in temperature. For lipophilic drug compounds that exhibit dissolution rate-limited absorption, these systems may offer an improvement in the rate and extent of absorption and result in more reproducible blood-time profiles (Gursoy and Benita 2004; Kovvasu et al. 2019; Salawi 2022).

A SEDDS formulation typically consists of a drug, oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant. The oil represents one of the most important excipients in the SEDDS formulation not only because it can solubilize marked amounts of the lipophilic drug or facilitate self-emulsification but also and mainly because it can increase the fraction of lipophilic drug transported via the intestinal lymphatic system, thereby increasing absorption from the GI tract depending on the molecular nature of the triglyceride. Medium-chain triglycerides (MCT) having carbon atoms between 6 and 12 are directly transported by portal blood to the systemic circulation. Whereas long-chain triglycerides (LCT) having more than 12 carbon atoms are transported via intestinal lymphatics. As MCTs have higher solvent capacity and are also not subjected to oxidation, they are widely used in lipid-based formulations (Gursoy and Benita 2004; Dokania and Joshi 2014).

Several compounds exhibiting surfactant properties may be employed for the design of self-emulsifying systems. The most widely recommended surfactants are non-ionic surfactants with a relatively high hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value. Various liquid or solid ethoxylated polyglycolized glycerides and polyoxyethylene 20 oleate (Tween 80) are the most frequently used excipients. Non-ionic surfactants are known to be less toxic compared to ionic surface-active agents, but they may cause moderate reversible changes in intestinal wall permeability. The surfactant concentration ranges between 30% and 60% (w/w) in order to form stable SEDDS (Gursoy and Benita 2004; Chaus et al. 2013).

Co-surfactants reduce the interfacial tension to a negative value and form a flexible interfacial film, thus acquiring different curvatures necessary for microemulsion formulations over a wide range of compositions. Organic co-surfactants, suitable for oral administration (ethanol,

propylene glycol (PG), polyethylene glycol (PEG), etc.), may help to dissolve large amounts of either the hydrophilic surfactant or the drug in the lipid base. The production of an optimum SEDDS requires relatively high concentrations (generally more than 30% w/w) of surfactants (Gursoy and Benita 2004; Chaus et al. 2013).

A number of potential mechanisms for enhancing the bioavailability of lipophilic drugs are suggested. SEDDS are reducing the gastric transit and, in this way, increasing the time available for dissolution. Effective luminal drug solubility is also increased by the presence of lipids, forming intestinal mixed micelles and thereby increasing the solubilization capacity of the GI tract. SEDDS enhance the lymphatic transport for lipophilic drugs and increase bioavailability directly or indirectly by reducing the first-pass metabolism. SEDDS also enhance the drug and peptide bioavailability by increasing membrane fluidity, the opening of tight junctions, and inhibition of P-glycoprotein and CYP450. SEDDS lead to the formulation of chylomicrons, which are absorbed primarily through the lymphatic system, thus avoiding the first-pass metabolism (Kumar et al. 2010; Dokania and Joshi 2014; Kovvasu et al. 2019).

The aim of the present study is to investigate how the combination of medium-chain and long-chain triglyceride oils with surfactants (Tween 80 and Cremophor RH-40) and co-surfactants (ethanol, PEG 400, and propylene glycol) affect the stability, physicochemical, technological, and biopharmaceutical characteristics of the prepared self-emulsifying drug delivery systems.

Materials and methods

Ibuprofen is obtained from FOT LTD. MCT Oil (containing 59% caprylic acid, 40% capric acid, and 1% lauric acid) is obtained from FutuNatura Dietary Supplements. Olive oil, castor oil, sesame oil, sunflower oil, Tween 80, Cremophor RH-40, propylene glycol, ethanol, and methanol are obtained from FOT LTD. All reagents and chemicals used are of analytical grade.

Methods

Solubility studies

The solubility of Ibuprofen in various oils, surfactants, and co-surfactants has been studied to select the formulations. A modified method described by Roni and Jalil (2011) has been used. The study has been conducted by mixing 5 ml of the oil/surfactant/co-surfactant with an excess amount of Ibuprofen in test tubes. The mixtures are mixed using a vortex mixer (Argo Lab Mix, Carpi, Italy) for 30 minutes and then sonicated for 2 hours to reach equilibrium. The equilibrated samples are centrifuged (DLAB DM0412, Beijing, China) at 3000 rpm for 20 minutes. The samples are filtered, and the filtrate is suitably diluted with methanol and analyzed by UV spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Evolution 300 UV-VIS, Waltham, USA) at 222 nm.

Compatibility studies

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

Compatibility studies between Ibuprofen, oil, surfactants, and co-surfactants have been studied by FTIR (InfraRed Bruker Tensor 37, Billerica, USA). All SEDDS formulations have been placed in ATR crystals. All samples have been scanned from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} using an FTIR spectrophotometer and compared with pure Ibuprofen.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The compatibility between Ibuprofen, oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant has been studied by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (Discovery DSC 250, TA Instruments, USA). Liquid samples have been placed in a Tzero Aluminum Hermetic pan with an empty cell as a blank. SEDDS formulations have been compared to pure Ibuprofen. All samples have been scanned at a temperature ramp speed of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and heat flow from 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for pure Ibuprofen).

Construction of pseudoternary phase diagram

Pseudoternary phase diagrams are constructed to examine the formation of oil-in-water emulsions using three components: oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant, which are selected based on the solubility study (Wen et al. 2021). Surfactant and co-surfactant (Smix) in each group are mixed in different weight ratios (3:1, 2:1, 1:1, 1:2). For each phase diagram, oil and a specific Smix ratio are mixed thoroughly in different weight ratios (9:1, 8:2, 7:3, 6:4, 5:5, 4:6, 3:7, 2:8, 1:9) so that maximum ratios are covered for the study. The mixtures are then observed visually for transparency and easy-flowing microemulsion. Pseudoternary phase diagrams are then constructed.

Preparation of Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS

Based on the solubility, emulsification ability, and pseudo-ternary phase diagram studies, excipients are selected. Twelve different formulations have been selected, consisting of Ibuprofen, oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant (Table 1). Dissolution has been conducted using a magnetic stirrer at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for solubilization to obtain a clear solution. The solutions are used to fill hard gelatin capsules, size 0 (Penjuri et al. 2017).

Table 1. Compositions of Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS.

Component	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Ibuprofen	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
Vitamin E	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
MCT Oil	0.120	0.120	0.120	0.060	0.120	0.120	0.120	0.060	–	0.060	–	0.060
Sunflower Oil	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.120	0.060	–	–
Olive Oil	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.120	0.060
Tween 80	0.360	0.360	0.360	0.360	–	–	–	–	0.360	0.360	0.360	0.360
Cremophor RH-40	–	–	–	–	0.360	0.360	0.360	0.360	–	–	–	–
Ethanol	0.120	–	–	–	0.120	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
PEG 400	–	0.120	–	–	–	0.120	–	–	–	–	–	–
Propylene glycol	–	–	0.120	0.180	–	–	0.120	0.180	0.120	0.120	0.120	0.120

Thermodynamic stability studies

Centrifugation

The selected Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS formulations are centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 30 minutes, followed by visual observation to confirm instability, including cracking, phase separation, drug precipitation, or creaming. The formulations without any signs of instability are subjected to the heating and cooling cycle (Saritha et al. 2014).

Heating and cooling cycle

The heating and cooling cycle has been done in six cycles between refrigerator temperatures of 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with storage at each temperature for not less than 48 hours. The formulations that are stable in such conditions without signs of creaming and phase separation are subjected to the freezing and thawing cycle (Saritha et al. 2014).

Freezing and thawing cycle

The freezing and thawing cycle has been done in six cycles between -20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a minimum of 48 hours storage duration. The formulations that are stable in such conditions have been further analyzed (Saritha et al. 2014).

Dispersibility test

One dose of Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS has been placed in 500 ml of purified water at 37 ± 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using an electromagnetic stirrer rotating at 100 rpm. Dispersibility is assessed visually using the following scoring system, in which Grade A and Grade B are considered optimal:

Grade A: Rapid formation (<1 minute) of a clear or light blue nanoemulsion;

Grade B: Rapid formation of a less clear emulsion with a bluer color;

Grade C: Formation of fine milky emulsion within 2 minutes;

Grade D: Formation of opaque, gray-white emulsion in more than 2 minutes;

Grade E: Low or minimal emulsification ability (Penjuri et al. 2017).

Drug precipitation study

Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS have been taken into 250 ml of purified water and mixed under continuous stirring using an electromagnetic stirrer rotating at 100 rpm. The formed emulsions are then observed visually after a period of 24 hours for the precipitation of the drug. The SEDDS are considered stable (without precipitation) or unstable (with precipitation) (Penjuri et al. 2017).

Accelerated stability study of Ibuprofen

A stability study has been carried out at 40 ± 2 °C and $75 \pm 5\%$ humidity for 90 days. The formulations have been analyzed for spontaneity of emulsification on the 0th and 90th days and drug content determination on the 30th, 60th, and 90th days. The average values of 3 measurements were taken (Parthasarathi et al. 2011).

Evaluation of SEDDS

Drug content

Ibuprofen from 1 dose of pre-weighed SEDDS is dissolved in methanol and analyzed using a UV spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 222 nm. The study has been repeated three times, and mean values have been taken (Penjuri et al. 2017).

Percent transmittance

An amount of the mixture containing 100 mg of Ibuprofen has been dispersed in 500 ml of purified water, 0.1M HCl, and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer on an electromagnetic stirrer at 100 rpm. The percent transmittance of formulations has been measured at 650 nm using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Purified water, 0.1M HCl, and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, respectively, have been used as a blank (Penjuri et al. 2017).

Droplet size and zeta potential

The mean globule size, zeta potential, and polydispersity index of SEDDS have been measured by a photon correlation spectroscopy instrument (Zetasizer Pro Red, Malvern Panalytical, Malvern, United Kingdom) at 25 °C. For measurement, SEDDS formulations have been pre-diluted hundredfold with distilled water. The particle size and size distribution study have been repeated 10 times, and the zeta potential measurement has been repeated 5 times, and average values have been taken (Khasia and Khasia 2012).

In vitro release study

The *in vitro* release of the optimized formulations (hard capsules filled with SEDDS), hard capsules filled with 200 mg pure Ibuprofen powder, and commercial product containing 200 mg Ibuprofen in the form of soft gelatin capsules is carried out using a USP type II dissolution apparatus in 900 ml pH 6.8 phosphate buffer (dissolution medium) maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C with the paddle rotating at 50 rpm. Samples (5 ml) are withdrawn at 15, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120, 180, and 240 minutes, and the same volume of fresh dissolution medium is replaced to maintain sink condition. The samples are filtered, diluted, and analyzed using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Evolution 300 UV-VIS, Waltham, USA) at 222 nm. Dissolution studies are performed, and the mean cumulative percentage of Ibuprofen is calculated and plotted against time. The average values of 3 measurements were taken (Sumit et al. 2024).

Results

Solubility studies

The solubility of Ibuprofen in various oils, surfactants, and co-surfactants is shown in Table 2. Among the oils, MCT oil, sunflower oil, and olive oil have shown the highest solubility, with 114.8 ± 0.23 , 111.9 ± 0.57 , and 110.8 ± 1.08 mg/ml, respectively, and are selected as the oil phase. Cremophor RH-40 and Tween 80 has shown the highest solubility with 218.3 ± 1.24 and 122.3 ± 0.38 , respectively, and are selected as the surfactants. The solubility of Ibuprofen in the oil and surfactant is important, as the maximum solubilization of the drug occurs in these phases. All studied co-solvents (PEG 400, propylene glycol, and ethanol) have shown good solubility – between 70 and 85 mg/ml.

Compatibility studies

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

The FTIR spectra of pure Ibuprofen and Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS (Fig. 1) indicate no chemical changes in the structure of Ibuprofen. All compositions retain the typical peaks of Ibuprofen, but with variations. The small changes in the intensity suggest physical interactions between Ibuprofen

Table 2. Solubility of Ibuprofen in various vehicles.

Vehicle	Solubility (mg/ml)	Vehicle	Solubility (mg/ml)
MCT Oil	114.8 ± 0.23	Cremophor RH-40	218.3 ± 1.24
Sesame Oil	94.3 ± 0.23	Tween 80	122.3 ± 0.38
Sunflower Oil	111.9 ± 0.57	Tween 20	78.0 ± 0.36
Olive Oil	110.8 ± 1.08	PEG 400	85.2 ± 0.25
Castor Oil	79.4 ± 0.17	Propylene glycol	72.7 ± 0.06
MCT Oil + Sunflower Oil 1:1	113.4 ± 0.4	Methanol	72.1 ± 0.69
MCT Oil + Olive Oil 1:1	112.8 ± 0.66	Ethanol	70.9 ± 0.50

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of Ibuprofen and SEDDS formulations.

and the SEDDS components. The peak of the C = O bond ($\sim 1720\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is most sensitive to these interactions; there are possibly weak hydrogen bonds formed between Ibuprofen and the carriers. All mixtures suppose physical, not chemical, solvation. The peaks at higher frequencies ($\sim 3200\text{--}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are not observed in pure Ibuprofen and are due to the presence of surfactants and co-solvents.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The DSC thermograms of Formulations 1, 5, 6, 7, and 8 (Fig. 2) show similarities to those of pure Ibuprofen. Due to the strong endothermic peak at $75\text{--}77\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, it can be suggested that pure Ibuprofen is present mostly in crystalline form. The SEDDS formulations decrease the enthalpy of melting, therefore disrupting the crystal structure. Partial solvation in the lipid phase or in the surfactant is observed, as well as a decrease in crystal size. Amorphous regions are present. The lowest enthalpy in formulations 6 and 8 indicates that Ibuprofen is dissolved to the highest extent, from which it can be assumed that they will achieve the highest bioavailability. The presence of broad endothermic effects $< 30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are related to the thermal behavior of the oils and surfactants, not to Ibuprofen.

Figure 2. DSC thermograms of Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS and pure Ibuprofen.

Construction of pseudoternary phase diagrams

The constructed pseudoternary phase diagrams for different oil-surfactant-co-surfactant systems are shown in Fig. 3. It has been found that at lower concentrations of the oil phase (MCT oil, olive oil, sunflower oil, or a combination of them) and higher concentrations of the surfactant (Tween 80 or Cremophor RH-40) and co-surfactant (ethanol, PEG 400, or propylene glycol), clearer, transparent, and stable emulsions are formed. The use of Cremophor RH-40 as a surfactant promotes the formation of wider microemulsion area in the pseudoternary phase diagrams compared to Tween 80. A higher surfactant concentration (surfactant:co-surfactant ratios 3:1 and 2:1) leads to an increase in the microemulsifying ability and the self-emulsifying area. Propylene glycol as a co-solvent also increases the microemulsion area as it stabilizes the formation of clear, transparent or slightly opalescent microemulsions at higher oil phase concentrations (70–90%). The ratios at which the self-emulsifying drug delivery systems have been prepared are selected based on the regions of the pseudoternary phase diagrams where the most stable and clear emulsions are formed.

Thermodynamic stability studies

The thermodynamic stability studies results are shown in Table 3. All compositions successfully pass the centrifugation test. The formulations containing medium-chain triglycerides show better stability and successfully pass the heating/cooling cycle, freeze-thaw test, and drug precipitation test, unlike compositions containing long-chain triglycerides (olive oil and sunflower oil). A relationship can be deduced between the choice of oil phase and the thermodynamic stability of SEDDS – medium-chain triglycerides provide higher stability.

The dispersibility test (Table 4) shows better dispersibility for the compositions containing medium-chain triglycerides, which form clear transparent or slightly opalescent emulsions in purified water (Fig. 4). The emulsifying ability is significantly improved in 0.1M HCl and in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

Figure 3. Pseudoternary phase diagrams.

Accelerated stability study of Ibuprofen

The results of the accelerated stability study of Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS show significant differences depending on the formulations (Fig. 5). The formulations containing medium-chain triglycerides show a tendency for higher stability. Formulations 5-8, containing Cremophor

RH-40 as surfactant, retain the quantitative content of Ibuprofen to a higher extent, with a significant decrease observed between the second and third months. Out of the remaining formulations, formulation 9, containing sunflower oil, Tween 80, and propylene glycol, is characterized by relatively high stability. All formulations retain their emulsifying ability after 3 months. A relationship is

Table 3. Results of thermodynamic stability studies.

Formulation	Centrifugation test	Heating/cooling cycle	Freeze-thaw test	Drug precipitation
F1	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
F2	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
F3	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
F4	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
F5	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
F6	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
F7	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
F8	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
F9	Pass	Fail	Fail	Fail
F10	Pass	Fail	Fail	Fail
F11	Pass	Fail	Fail	Fail
F12	Pass	Fail	Fail	Fail

Table 4. Results of dispersion grade and percent transmittance studies.

Formulation	Dispersion grade (water)	Dispersion grade (0.1M HCl)	Dispersion grade (pH 6.8 phosphate buffer)	Percent transmittance (water)	Percent transmittance (0.1M HCl)	Percent transmittance (pH 6.8 phosphate buffer)
F1	A	A	A	98.2	99.7	99.8
F2	A	A	A	98.8	99.8	99.6
F3	A	A	A	98.5	99.7	99.7
F4	A	A	A	98.8	99.7	99.8
F5	B	A	A	94.8	94.3	93.7
F6	A	A	A	97.6	99.6	99.2
F7	B	A	A	96.5	98.4	98.1
F8	A	A	A	97.3	99.5	99.5
F9	C	A	B	8.7	92.5	64.8
F10	B	A	A	40.8	91.8	89.5
F11	C	B	B	11.9	59.0	70.9
F12	B	A	A	49.4	86.2	92.4

observed between the choice of surfactant and the stability of self-emulsifying systems. Cremophor RH-40 provides relatively higher stability.

Evaluation of SEDDS

Drug content

The results of the drug content evaluations are shown in Table 5. All SEDDS formulations show a quantitative content of Ibuprofen close to 100%.

Percent transmittance

The results of the percent transmittance test (Table 4) show higher values for formulations 1-8. The presence of medium-chain triglycerides as the oil phase in these compositions results in a transmittance close to 100%. The choice of surfactant and co-surfactant does not affect the transmittance, as the results when comparing Tween 80 and Cremophor RH-40, as well as ethanol, PEG 400, and propylene glycol, are similar. From this information it can be concluded that the formed emulsions have nano-sized particles. This has been confirmed by the Zetasizer study. The transmittance is even higher in 0.1M HCl and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, from which it

can be suggested that the particle sizes are even smaller in physiological environments.

Droplet size and zeta potential

The results of the droplet size and zeta potential analysis are shown in Table 6. The average particle size is small and uniform in the formulations containing medium-chain tri-

Figure 4. Appearance of microemulsions formed from formulations 4 and 8 after dilution.

Table 5. Drug content results.

Formulation	Drug content (%)	Formulation	Drug content (%)
Formulation 1	101.9 ± 0.8	Formulation 7	97.5 ± 0.4
Formulation 2	101.8 ± 1.4	Formulation 8	96.4 ± 0.3
Formulation 3	100.3 ± 0.5	Formulation 9	100.9 ± 0.5
Formulation 4	100.1 ± 0.3	Formulation 10	99.1 ± 0.5
Formulation 5	97.6 ± 0.5	Formulation 11	96.3 ± 0.3
Formulation 6	96.0 ± 0.4	Formulation 12	97.0 ± 0.5

Table 6. Results of Zetasizer Pro Red analysis and percent transmittance.

Formulation	Average size (nm)	Polydispersity Index	Zeta-potential (mV)	Conductivity (mS/cm)
F1	$d_1 = 18.66 \pm 0.21$	0.089	+7.45 ± 4.08	0.023
F2	$d_1 = 20.62 \pm 0.25$	0.090	+4.40 ± 1.31	0.023
F3	$d_1 = 25.25 \pm 1.97$	0.230	+1.45 ± 0.88	0.022
	$d_2 = 323.2 \pm 207.40$			
F4	$d_1 = 14.63 \pm 0.05$	0.120	+7.96 ± 1.04	0.021
F5	$d_1 = 37.27 \pm 0.72$	0.170	-1.89 ± 0.38	0.025
F6	$d_1 = 29.35 \pm 0.41$	0.097	+1.77 ± 1.25	0.030
F7	$d_1 = 32.29 \pm 0.40$	0.130	+1.83 ± 2.50	0.020
F8	$d_1 = 22.72 \pm 0.33$	0.095	+5.47 ± 2.65	0.026
F9	$d_1 = 12.61 \pm 1.89$	0.690	-0.107 ± 0.62	0.020
	$d_2 = 1137 \pm 142.30$			
F10	$d_1 = 17.35 \pm 2.85$	0.860	-0.40 ± 0.18	0.022
	$d_2 = 61.74 \pm 7.91$			
	$d_3 = 1099.0 \pm 126.0$			
F11	$d_1 = 11.76 \pm 0.83$	0.750	+7.46 ± 0.25	0.020
	$d_2 = 1141.0 \pm 82.85$			
F12	$d_1 = 15.08 \pm 1.74$	1.0	+1.91 ± 0.40	0.020
	$d_2 = 72.72 \pm 7.88$			
	$d_3 = 428.80 \pm 23.0$			
	$d_4 = 702.3 \pm 7 \times 10^{-6}$			
	$d_5 = 866.0 \pm 0$			

Figure 5. Amount of undegraded Ibuprofen ($n = 3$, $P \leq 0.05$).

glycerides (F1-F8) – approximately 14.63–37.27 nm. Formulations containing long-chain triglycerides (F9-F12) show a multimodal distribution, including significantly larger fractions (up to over 1000 nm). This suggests aggregation and unstable dispersions. The low polydispersity index (0.089–0.230) in formulations 1–8, containing medium-chain triglycerides, indicates the formation of monodisperse systems. The presence of long-chain triglycerides in formulations 9–12 leads to an increase in the polydispersity index (Fig. 6). It can be assumed that the uniform particle size distribution is mainly due to the choice of oil phase. A certain dependence is observed between the concentration of the oil phase

and the particle size. Formulations 4 and 8, in which the amount of the oil phase is 8.5%, show a smaller particle size (14.63–22.72 nm), a low polydispersity index, and a relatively high zeta potential. This may be due to the improved solubility of Ibuprofen and the surfactant in the presence of a higher concentration of propylene glycol. Zeta potential plays an important role in the interactions with mucus of the gastrointestinal tract. Most compositions are with a positive charge with zeta potential values being in the range of ± 0.107 –7.96 mV. The highest values are shown by formulations 1, 4, 8, and 11. The results correlate with those obtained by other authors (Penjuri et al. 2017). The stability of the studied formulations is most likely determined not by the zeta potential values, but the steric stabilization resulting from the use of nonionic surfactants (Sharma et al. 2014). The conductivity values are close to 0 in all formulations, meaning that no changes in electrical conductivity are observed.

In vitro release study

The *in vitro* release study results (Fig. 7) show that all formulations have a rapid initial release during the first 30–45 minutes. After 60 minutes, the curves level off, reaching a plateau. The use of Cremophor RH-40 as a surfactant provides a slightly delayed release but a higher rate of release

Figure 6. Size distribution by intensity.

Figure 7. In vitro dissolution profiles of Ibuprofen-loaded SEDDS ($n = 3$, $P \leq 0.05$).

compared to the formulations containing Tween 80 as a surfactant. The best results are shown by formulations 6, 7, and 8, containing medium-chain triglycerides, Cremophor RH-40, and PEG 400 or propylene glycol as co-surfactant, reaching over 90% of Ibuprofen released after 60 minutes. This information suggests good self-emulsifying ability, probably an optimal oil/surfactant/co-surfactant ratio, and a stable micellar system. Compared to the standard and the marketed product, formulations 6, 7, and 8 show improved

Ibuprofen release profiles. A relationship is observed between particle size and the rate and extent of release.

Conclusion

The study conducted on Ibuprofen-loaded self-emulsifying drug delivery systems clearly shows that the systems based on medium-chain triglycerides and suitable surfactants

represent a promising approach for improving the stability, solubility, and release of poorly water-soluble drugs. The results of the FTIR analysis confirm the absence of chemical interactions between Ibuprofen and the components of the SEDDS, which suggests a stability of the molecular structure of the active substance and good compatibility with the lipid matrix. The DSC analysis further supports these results, showing that the inclusion of Ibuprofen in the SEDDS leads to a significant decrease in the enthalpy of melting and partial amorphization. The most significant effects are observed in formulations 6 and 8, in which the drug substance is most dissolved in the lipid phase. This means improved solubility, faster release, and potentially higher bioavailability.

The results of the thermodynamic stability studies and accelerated stability study highlight the significant advantage of medium-chain triglycerides, which provide higher physical and chemical stability of the formulations. Cremophor RH-40 in particular stands out as an effective surfactant, contributing to the preservation of the quantitative content of Ibuprofen and the preservation of the emulsifying ability.

The evaluation of SEDDS in terms of transmittance, particle size, and zeta-potential demonstrates the formation of nanodispersed systems with an average size of 14.63–37.27 nm and a low polydispersity index in the systems containing medium-chain triglycerides. Stable monodisperse systems have been formed. This is a key factor for rapid emulsification and dispersion stability, while formulations containing long-chain triglycerides show a tendency to aggregation.

Finally, the *in vitro* release results clearly demonstrate the superiority of formulations 6, 7, and 8, containing medium-chain triglycerides, Cremophor RH-40, and PEG 400/propylene glycol, which achieve over 90% released Ibuprofen in 60 minutes and outperform both the standard formulation and the marketed product. This data confirms that the optimal combination of oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant can significantly improve the physicochemical, technological, and biopharmaceutical characteristics of Ibuprofen and lead to the development of a highly effective self-emulsifying drug delivery system.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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